

Professional online education processes: Analyzing self-efficacy and low self-efficacy

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ABSTRACT

Students with high self-efficacy tend to procrastinate less often than students with low self-efficacy. In addition, the demandas del contexto determinadas por la structure of instructional suport estan relacionada con la construcción de conocimiento profesional tácito o explícito. The present study explored self-efficacy and structure of instructional suport in professional online education processes on 61 graduate students who participated in a course to improve their professional competence. Two noteworthy results have been found; on the one hand, the characterization of electronic communications of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy as brief and mainly adress to other students but no to teacher, and on the other hand, the relationship between the type of knowledge construct, this is tacit and explicit, and the level of self-efficacy. Thus, to maintain students' efforts, follow up and level of satisfaction in order to finish an online course, it is necessary that teachers pay

close attention to fragments of discourse verbalizing self-efficacy and low self-efficacy and the structure of the instructional support.

Key words: professional learning, online teaching-learning process, self-efficacy, tacit knowledge, implicit knowledge.

1. INTRODUCTION

Online teaching-learning processes aimed at increasing professional competencies have been receiving attention from researchers (Hirumi, 2002a; Hirumi, 2002b; Brosnan & Burgess, 2003; Engeström, Engeström, & Kerosou, 2003; Borko, 2004; Tillema, 2005). In this article, we highlight two concepts; self-efficacy (Bandura, 2005; Zimmerman, 2002; Lee, Choi & Kang, 2009; Cho & Jonassen, 2010) and the importance of the type of activities that students are required to carry out throughout their learning, tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge (Nonaka, 1988, 1990, 1991 1994). It is important to consider self-efficacy in online teaching and learning processes because self-efficacy has been linked with coping behavior, how much effort will be expended and how long it will be sustained when facing obstacles and aversive experiences. In this regard, it is appropriate to take into account the contributions made by the dynamic theory of organizational knowledge creation: this theory establishes two types of knowledge according to the demands of context: tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge.

2. PROFESSIONAL ONLINE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESSES: TACIT

AND IMPLICIT KNOWLEDGE

The dynamic theory of organizational knowledge creation (Nonaka, 1988; 1990; 1991; 1994) is divided into tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge. “Explicit or codified knowledge refers to knowledge that is transmittable in formal, systematic language, while tacit knowledge has a personal quality which makes it hard to formalize and communicate. Tacit knowledge is deeply rooted in action, commitment and involvement in a specific context” (Nonaka, 1994, p.16). The differentiation between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge is important; the professions verbalize different contents depending on whether an activity elicits tacit knowledge or explicit knowledge. The fragments of discourse that professionals verbalize during, and at the end of the teaching-learning process are different if the nature of the activity is tacit or explicit. It is relevant to consider the type of knowledge being constructed, especially if one wants to analyze the expectations, beliefs, estimates and judgments of one's own knowledge and the perception of efficacy. In this sense it is expected that, if a professional has built tacit knowledge and finds himself or herself facing a task that demands explicit knowledge, their perception of efficacy will be lower than that of a professional who has built tacit knowledge and is confronted by a task that elicits tacit knowledge.

The behaviors that students exhibit in online learning environments, for example, the number of electronic communications they send to their peers and teachers in all areas of the classroom and the readings they conduct in the messages from their peers and teachers (Shin, 2002; Shin, 2003), are linked to the specific online learning environment. These

behaviors are related to the type of environment: the relevance of each behavior is associated with the precise environment; therefore, specific behaviors are associated to particular situations. This significance focuses on the access that students and teachers have to technology and the influence this has on learning, rather than on the actual interaction between students and technology (Anderson & Ronnkvist, 1999; McKlin, Harmon, Evans & Jone, 2001; Watson, Kelly, Callingham & Shaughnessy, 2003; Noss & Hoyles, 2004; Way, 2006).

2.1. Online self-efficacy and professional teaching and learning processes

Since Bandura (1977) introduced the concept of self-efficacy, which is the individual belief that one can persevere despite challenges, several important studies have been carried out in relation to online education. The self-efficacy theory assigned self-efficacy a central role in analyzing changes achieved to fearful and avoidant behavior. “This theory is based on the principal assumption that psychological procedures, whatever their form, serve as a means of creating and strengthening expectations of personal efficacy. Within this analysis, efficacy expectations are distinguished from response-outcome expectancies” (Bandura, 1977, p. 193). “Perceived self-efficacy is defined as people’s beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise influence over events that affect their lives” (Bandura, 1994, p. 71) According to the social cognitive theory, an expectant outcome is defined as a student’s estimate that a given behavior will lead to certain outcomes. An efficacy expectation is the conviction that one can successfully execute the behavior required to produce the outcomes. Outcome and efficacy expectations are

differentiated because individuals can believe that a particular course of action will produce certain outcomes, but if they entertain serious doubts about whether they can perform the necessary activities, such information does not influence their behavior.

Contrary to the common belief that behavior is controlled by its immediate consequences, behavior is related to its outcomes at the level of aggregate consequences rather than momentary effects (Baum, 1973). Self-efficacy beliefs, as evidenced in discourse, act as a motivational influence and affect individual action, performance and behavior. In essence, self-efficacy has a mediating influence on behavior, and specifically on whether a behavioral task is attempted at all, the effort put into the activity and into persisting with that task. Bandura's self-efficacy theory (1977) is based on the assumption that psychological procedures, whatever their form, serve as a means of creating and strengthening expectations of personal efficacy. Efficacy expectations and outcome expectations are relevant concepts of this theory. An efficacy expectation is the conviction that one can successfully execute the behavior required to produce the outcomes. Outcome expectation is defined as a person's estimate that a given behavior will lead to certain outcomes. For example, a student can verbalize that a particular response given in an activity is inadequate which will result in not successfully passing this activity. This means that if students believe they cannot succeed in specific tasks (low self-efficacy), they will attempt them only superficially, give up quickly, avoid or resist them. To analyze self-efficacy, the three dimensions of efficacy expectations must be considered. These dimensions are: magnitude, generality and strength. Magnitude considers that when the tasks are ordered by level of difficulty, different individuals' efficacy expectations may be

limited to the simpler tasks, extended to moderately difficult ones, or included in even the most taxing performance. Generality refers to some experiences that instill a more generalized sense of efficacy that extends well beyond the specific treatment situation, and strength is defined as weak expectations which are easily extinguishable by uncomfortable experiences, whereas individuals who possess strong expectations of mastery will persevere in their coping efforts despite the uncomfortable experiences.

Self-efficacy on online teaching and learning process have been analyzed. This research into self-efficacy and online teaching-learning processes has recently received attention because of the need to analyze the use of computerized environments involving an ensemble of interaction involving cognitive, social, educational and technological aspects (Hannafin & Land, 1997; Anderson & Garrison, Azevedo, 2005; Ejilifes, 2009; Artino & Stephens, 2009). Cheng-Yuan & Lea (2001) distinguish two types of self-efficacy: self-efficacy for course content and self-efficacy for online learning technology. These researchers pointed out that in order to be motivated and successful in an online course, students should possess high self-efficacy for the content being taught. Hiltz & Shea (2005) studied the profile of online learners and found that their individual objective and psychological characteristics were related to the likelihood of success in online courses (as defined by high learner satisfaction and good grades). The psychological characteristics include self-efficacy, motivation and personal expectations. These factors, along with some others, were included in the later study. Experience and ability with computers have also been related to self-efficacy; if students show low self-efficacy there may be motivational problems in the accomplishment of the tasks (Margolis & McCabe, 2006). La relación entre

el perfil del estudiante online y la autoeficacia también ha sido analizada. Por ejemplo, XX analizan las diferencias de autoeficacia en hombres y mujeres hallando que y XXX analizan las diferencias de autoeficacia entre undergraduate students and graduate students hallando que....

Sin embargo, la mayoría de investigaciones analizan la autoeficacia a partir de los datos obtenidos mediante cuestionarios tanto la autoeficacia en relación a los propios elementos del curso () como la autoeficacia hacia las tecnologías (). Destacamos dos ejemplos: el Internet Self-Efficacy Scale (ISES) and the Online Self-Regulated Learning Inventory (OSRLI). Two studies focusing on the development and validation of the OSRLI were conducted by Jonassen (2010). The OSRLI is a self-report instrument assessing the human interaction dimension of online self-regulated learning. It consists of an affect/motivation scale and an interaction strategies scale.. Those studies yielded affect/motivation factors (enjoyment of human interaction, self-efficacy for interaction with instructors, concern for interaction with students, and self-efficacy for contributing to the online community) and initial learning strategies (writing strategies, responding strategies, and reflection strategies).

In spite of this, it will be proposed analizar la autoeficacia a partir de las comunicaciones de los alumnos sin preguntarles directamente por su autoeficacia.

The relationship between self-efficacy and knowledge construction requires more investigation. This line of research has been revived in the analysis of professionalizing

processes in online teaching-learning because this virtual teaching-learning environment has been considered particularly difficult; this environment requires students to analyze the learning situation, establish learning objectives and make plans. A systematic observation of the virtual classroom shows us evidence that students spontaneously verbalize expectations, beliefs, feelings and judgments in relation to the task and their own sense of perception of achievement in a specific course. However, in the light of recent research, which clearly links the learning environment to student and educator behavior throughout the online teaching-learning process, we consider that it is essential to analyze self-efficacy without altering the environment. In other words, it is important that self-efficacy is not influenced by any measuring instruments introduced into the learning process, such as psychological tests. Self-efficacy should be analyzed as it appears spontaneously in students' communications, whether in messages sent between them or in messages sent to the teacher and, even including activities that must be performed throughout the course.

3. AIM

As we have seen, research into teaching and learning processes highlights the importance of analyzing these processes in connection to tacit and explicit knowledge. In many cases, self-efficacy among students is basically founded on participants' opinions or in answers elicited by questionnaires, making it difficult to incorporate new scientifically-proven knowledge into the framework of the profession. With the objective of incorporating up-to-date and valid professional knowledge based on observation, this study analyzes the teaching-learning processes of a higher education environmental science course, focusing on the type

of activity and self-efficacy. Additionally, influential elements have been extracted from the teaching-learning processes and suggestions made for improvements to the design and planning of online courses in order to increase the cognitive benefits that may be obtained.

4. METHODOLOGY

The educational context allows students to reflect on their practice, relating the theoretical content to their activity; the workplace therefore is an ideal context for the emergence of professional discourse. Furthermore, if the educational context is an interactive learning environment, then the discourse is fully recorded, facilitating a comprehensive analysis. For this reason, we chose to segment and codify teaching and learning discourse that emerged during the progress of an online professional practice development course. We also identified fragments of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy contained in the students' messages and activities, while also taking into account the societal and broad institutional frameworks. The following sections detail the method employed, specifically the units of analysis, the participants, instruments and research procedure.

4.1. Unit of analysis

In accordance with Engeström, the unit of analysis is the activity system. The activity system in this research is one which is developed around two activities (a formative one and an evaluative one), with the environmental science content applied to management and based on interaction. This unit of analysis should be fragmented in order to analyze the

verbalization of self-efficacy in the online debates and activities. Additionally, fragments must clearly reflect Bandura's self-efficacy concept. This means that speech fragments were identified as units when they had a basis for use; therefore, they were units of discursive communication without changes of discursive subject, without changes of style or form and with the same procedure. The fragment could vary in length, from one sentence to a whole paragraph, but it was necessary to maintain said similarities.

4.2. Participants

The participants were last semester students taking a human resources degree. The 61 students (x MEN AND x WOMAN) who participated in the investigation had prior experience and specific training in human resources. All the participants had professional experience, especially in business (Mean=2, SD=0.008). These characteristics are very relevant in the sense that they were necessary to guarantee that participants were higher education students despite being involved in a course to develop their professional practice. If this characteristic had not been fulfilled, the recorded speech could not have been considered as professional but rather as academic. Therefore, the participants were students with experience and training and the type of activity proposed was an authentic activity.

4.3. Instruments and data collection

In accordance with the theoretical framework and objectives of the research, no instruments were designed. To collect examples of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy, we considered it

necessary to analyze the students' spontaneous verbalization during the learning process. Thus, observation was carried out without interfering in the learning process; upon completing the course, the students were informed of the opportunity to participate in the research and the corresponding authorization was requested.

The investigation procedure did not interfere with the teaching-learning process designed and used by the teacher. The course instructor designed three activities: the first one elicited tacit professional discourse during the teaching-learning process (formative activity), the second one elicited tacit professional discourse after the teaching-learning process (assessment activity), and the third one elicited explicit professional discourse after the teaching-learning process (assessment activity). The formative activity presented a simulated problematic situation that could be managed if the students used the professional discourse contained in the course materials. In addition, the students had to use ecological footprint software which measures the size of humanity's demand on nature. The assessment activity simulated a problematic situation that could be managed if the students applied the professional discourse contained in the course materials (tacit) or theoretical questions that could be managed if the students used the professional discourse contained in the course materials (explicit).

In the time spent on the formative activity, the students had the chance to interact in various special groups and with the professor's personal mailbox. These spaces of interaction were planned by the professor as spaces for doubts, contributions and constructing combined knowledge. Once the formative activity was completed, the students could choose two

different dates to do their assessment activity: if they chose the first day of assessment, the activity elicited tacit professional discourse, and if they chose the second assessment day, the activity elicited explicit professional discourse. The students who carried out the assessment activity which elicited tacit professional discourse were assigned to group 1, while the students who carried out the assessment activity which elicited explicit professional discourse were assigned to group 2.

A database recording all the written online messages sent during the courses was created and it included the following different aspects: who sent the messages, who received the messages, the date and time of the messages, the mailbox used by the message sender, the full text and any attachments included. Data consisting of study material discourse to establish assessment criteria, electronic communications and documents produced by the students (formative activity and assessment activity) were also collected for analysis.

4.4. Procedure

The analysis procedure was aimed at ensuring the methodological rigor of the investigation; a three-phase analysis was established. The 2330 words contained in the formative activity and assessment activity and the 170 words produced by the students during the professional practice development course were analyzed. To be sure that we made good use of the criteria, a procedure for inter-observer reliability based on the Cohen Kappa index was established. High results were obtained: for codes Cohen's Kappa= 1; Spearman Rho=1; for fragments Cohen's Kappa= 0.82; Spearman Rho=0.99.

- Phase 1. Initial classroom observation to verify that the students verbalized fragments of self-efficacy. This first observation allowed the confirmation that, in the debate space, students had sent electronic communication which included fragments of self-efficacy.
- Phase 2. Elaboration of a protocol for observation based on the characterization of Bandura's (1977) self-efficacy. The characterization of Bandura's self-efficacy leads to the identification of fragments in terms of magnitude, generality and strength. Additionally, reliability was then calculated: a procedure for inter-observer reliability based on the Cohen Kappa and Spearman Rho was established. The calculation of reliability was carried out based on 10% of all the students' contributions. Thus, the calculation is based on the analysis of electronic communications and the production of six participants (three participants from group 1 and three participants from group 2).
- Phase 3. A mixed process of analysis was executed. The mixed analysis was carried out by analyzing the electronic communications and the production of the 61 students based on the observation and quantitative analysis protocol in order to calculate the significance of the differences between group 1 and 2. This quantitative analysis also aimed at characterizing the low self-efficacy fragments and the self-efficacy fragments.

5. RESULTS

We have found two noteworthy results; on the one hand, the characterization of electronic communications of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy, and on the other hand, the relationship between the type of activity (tacit and explicit) and the verbalization of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy.

Firstly, and in relation to the characteristics common between self-efficacy and low self-efficacy, it is important to point out that the fragments of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy appear in the interaction among the students and between the students and the educator, especially at the end of the teaching-learning process. A greater percentage of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy fragments were identified in the interaction between students (67%) than in students' interaction with the educator (20%) and in the learning outcomes (13%). The week before and the week after the evaluative activity is when 83% of the fragments showing self-efficacy and low self-efficacy appeared. It is important to highlight that these fragments of self-efficacy and low self-efficacy are not long, supported and complex messages; they are short messages that range from one to four sentences. All self-efficacy and low self-efficacy electronic communications referred to course content but not to online learning technology. We provide some examples in the following table:

Type of fragment **Participant** **Fragment** **Where** Self-efficacy Participant 1 (...) Personally, it wasn't that difficult for me.(...) Interaction student-teacher. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Self-efficacy Participant 5 Hello *teacher name*,

Participant **Fragment** **Where** Self-efficacy Participant 1 (...) Personally, it wasn't that difficult for me.(...) Interaction student-teacher. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Self-efficacy Participant 5 Hello *teacher name*,

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Participant 5 Hello *teacher name*,

Hello *teacher name*,

Although the activity was not difficult for me, it was surprising. I wasn't expecting it; the first activity was completely theoretical and the second seemed as though it were referring to a more specific and practical issue of the activity.(...)

Regards. Interaction student-teacher. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Self-efficacy Participant 8 (...) It seemed to me to be an interesting knowledge and awareness activity (...) Interaction student-teacher. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

Interaction student-teacher. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Self-efficacy Participant 8 (...) It seemed to me to be an interesting knowledge and awareness activity (...) Interaction student-teacher. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

Self-efficacy Participant 8 (...) It seemed to me to be an interesting knowledge and awareness activity (...) Interaction student-teacher. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

Self-efficacy Participant 8 (...) It seemed to me to be an interesting knowledge and awareness activity (...) Interaction student-teacher. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

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(...) It seemed to me to be an interesting knowledge and awareness activity (...) Interaction student-teacher. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

Interaction student-teacher. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

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Self-efficacy Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

Participant 25 Hello *teacher name* ,

Hello *teacher name* ,

Regarding the second question in the activity, after getting over my initial nervousness, I managed to focus the answer on the data I had calculated and worked on in the activity.(...)

Regards. Interaction student-teacher. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello *student name*,

Interaction student-teacher. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello *student name*,

Self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello *student name*,

Self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello *student name*,

Participant 32 Hello *student name*,

Hello *student name*,

I am finishing the theoretical part and I think I'll be able to send it to you this afternoon, even though I am finishing another activity for another class for this Tuesday.

Regards. Interaction student-student. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Low self-efficacy Participant 2 Please excuse the handwriting, *teacher name*. I am very stressed. I am not just stressed because of the activity, but because of the whole week. This week has been unbearable for me.

Interaction student-student. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Low self-efficacy Participant 2 Please excuse the handwriting, *teacher name*. I am very stressed. I am not just stressed because of the activity, but because of the whole week. This week has been unbearable for me.

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Low self-efficacy Participant 2 Please excuse the handwriting, *teacher name*. I am very stressed. I am not just stressed because of the activity, but because of the whole week. This week has been unbearable for me.

Participant 2 Please excuse the handwriting, *teacher name*. I am very stressed. I am not just stressed because of the activity, but because of the whole week. This week has been unbearable for me.

Please excuse the handwriting, *teacher name*. I am very stressed. I am not just stressed because of the activity, but because of the whole week. This week has been unbearable for me.

Best regards. Last paragraph of the activity 2. Low self-efficacy Participant 17 Is the case real? Otherwise, if it is not real, we can create one. There is no problem. But...my God, What about the length of the document! I'm worried about it.

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Best regards. Interaction student-student. During teaching-learning process (formative period). Low self-efficacy Participant 9 Hello,

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Participant 9 Hello,

Hello,

In today's quiz, the questions were:

1st) What is the function of qualitative techniques in social and vocational auditing?

2nd) What are the three levels of consumption of the ecological footprint? (I don't think I answered correctly...(with all due respect) because I only remember one (I didn't expect to see this question)

Regards. Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Low self-efficacy Participant 19 Hello everyone,

Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Low self-efficacy Participant 19 Hello everyone,

Low self-efficacy Participant 19 Hello everyone,

Low self-efficacy Participant 19 Hello everyone,

Participant 19 Hello everyone,

Hello everyone,

In my opinion, the question didn't make a lot of sense since it didn't have anything to do with the subject matter; the activity only asked us to use the method and to discuss the results. It didn't ask us to analyze its use. The method was a way to comment on the issue of social responsibility. So, I don't think I answered the question well.

Bad, very bad... Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Low self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello,

Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Low self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello,

Low self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello,

Low self-efficacy Participant 32 Hello,

Participant 32 Hello,

Hello,

I felt terrible when I saw the question, and to think that there were theoretical things, actually, I thought that the footprint was an entertaining and interesting thing in this practice. You wouldn't have believed the look on my face, but the die has been cast, we'll just have to wait and see what happens, I didn't do it well.

Participant 32's name. Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Low self-efficacy Participant 33 Hello (*name of teacher*),

Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Low self-efficacy Participant 33 Hello (*name of teacher*),

Low self-efficacy Participant 33 Hello (*name of teacher*),

Low self-efficacy Participant 33 Hello (*name of teacher*),

Participant 33 Hello (*name of teacher*),

Hello (*name of teacher*),

I came to the exam kind of upset, and with an extremely low level of concentration because from the 9th to the 14th I was in hospital with my two-month-old son who was admitted as a patient there. I thought the questions were easy. (...)

Thanks for your understanding. Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Table 1. Examples. Self-efficacy fragments and low self-efficacy fragments.

Interaction students-students. At the end of teaching-learning process (assessment period). Table 1. Examples.

Self-efficacy fragments and low self-efficacy fragments.

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Regarding the specific characterization of self-efficacy, 11 out of the 61 participants verbalized self-efficacy fragments (18%). Upon analyzing the co-occurrence between self-efficacy and magnitude, generality and strength, we found that no correlation was established between the self-efficacy fragments verbalizing the easiness of the activity. (Pearson correlation= 0.56; Spearman Rho= 0.43). When self-efficacy fragments appeared in the students' discourse, we did not then identify fragments referring to the activities as not being very difficult. Likewise, self-efficacy fragments were not followed by fragments extending efficacy to other situations either. However, fragments expressing the intention to continue working on an activity did appear after self-efficacy fragments.

In reference to the specific characterization of low self-efficacy, 12 out of the 61 (20%) participants verbalized low self-efficacy fragments. Additionally, we have found a correlation between low self-efficacy fragments and fragments that verbalize the difficulty of the activity (Pearson correlation= 0.82, Spearman Rho=0.92). This means that when low self-efficacy fragments appear in the students' discourse, we then identify reference to the difficulty of the activity 82% of the time. These fragments mix the affirmation of a part of the assessment task's level of difficulty with the affirmation of how students have given a wrong answer. Thus, they mix a value aspect of the assessment activity by linking it to their own low self-efficacy.

The samples of low self-efficacy were mostly produced during the assessment activity and after the assessment. However, the fragments referring to low self-efficacy, specifically those which are feelings of a lack of competence when facing a task, do not correspond to the level of constructing knowledge as shown in the student's professional discourse about

organizational ethics. While feelings of lacking competence in the assessment have been found in 21% of the participants, none of them were assessed as incompetent by the educator. In spite of verbalizing low self-efficacy, none of the participants responded to the assessment activity incorrectly. Low self-efficacy does not correspond with the level of knowledge construction that they truly possessed. It is important to keep in mind that this perception of difficulty does not correspond with the student's actual ability to respond to the activity.

Secondly, and in reference to the difference between group 1 and 2, out of the 61 students, 12 showed low self-efficacy; of these 12 students, 8 of them belonged to group 1, which is the group that executed a tacit activity during the learning process and an explicit activity during assessment. In group 2, which is the group that executed a tacit activity during the learning process and a tacit activity during assessment, 4 students showed low self-efficacy. When assessment involves the same type of requirements that the activity and the environment have contained during the course, 82% of professionals verbalize fragments of self-efficacy and 66% of professionals verbalize low self-efficacy while considering exactly the same learning content. However, when the assessment involves a change in the type of requirement from tacit to explicit, 33% of professionals verbalize self-efficacy fragments and 18% of professionals verbalize low self-efficacy. The results show that there are significant differences in the verbalization of self-efficacy when the type of activity elicits knowledge of a different type ($F=6.397$, $Sig=0.014$). Regarding the fragments of low self-efficacy, the results show less significant differences in the verbalization of low self-efficacy when the type of activity elicits knowledge of a different type ($F=1.346$,

Sig=0.251).

This result is quite noteworthy since all the students that showed low self-efficacy during assessment went through a learning process where the tacit activity had been changed to an explicit activity. Both of the activities asked questions regarding the same content that had been worked on during the process, but the students rated the process which involved a change from tacit to explicit as being much more difficult. This result can be interpreted, but given that explicit knowledge involves conscious verbalization, the added effort of verbalization was rated as low self-efficacy. This result is linked to other previous research which establishes that tacit knowledge is different from explicit knowledge, and that together they form the basis of different and complementary professional discourse.

On a methodological level, it is very important to point out that various authors (Pizifferro, 2008, Lin, 2008) have measured self-efficacy using a questionnaire; for example, the Academic Self-Regulation Questionnaire (Harde & Reeve, 2003) or the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (Lin, 2008). The Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) has been used frequently. MSLQ includes nine subscales: rehearsal, elaboration, organization, critical thinking, metacognitive self-regulation, time and study environment, effort regulation, peer learning and help seeking. In our understanding, this questionnaire, which is used to measure self-efficacy, rates aspects that go beyond this concept by entering into aspects that are traditionally metacognitive and self-regulating (Bandura, 1977; Flavell, 1979; Zimmerman, 2002). At the same time, as we understand it, the value of self-efficacy in the teaching-learning process lies in the fact that it can be a key

to identifying moments in which students lack self-motivation. These moments can lead to students dropping out of the online course in a few days. Therefore, it is important to pay attention to students' spontaneous verbalization because this is how key moments can be identified. Perceived self-efficacy ratings should be analyzed in students' spontaneous discourse.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Self-efficacy must be considered in order to improve the effectiveness of technology-enabled developmental models for improving students' outcomes. When fragments of self-efficacy discourse appear in the interaction between students, the teacher must pay close attention. These fragments are not very large but they clearly reflect feelings of low competence regarding the educational task. Thus, fragments of between 30 and 100 words are long enough to reflect the beliefs that occur before detachment behavior. Self-efficacy is one of the elements that must be considered in a more complex theoretical framework which includes interaction and presence. It is important to note that not all low-efficacy verbalizations are negative. For example, in data concerning exactly the same learning content, when students completed a formative tacit activity and evaluation tacit activity 82% of these professionals verbalized self-efficacy, and 66% of these professionals verbalized low self-efficacy. This means that students who verbalize low self-efficacy during the process can have a high sense of efficacy at the end of the learning process. In this sense, low efficacy should not only be interpreted as a negative factor.

An expression of low self-efficacy is prototypically brief, sent to classmates and accompanied by a demonstration of difficulty in the activity. This means that verbalizations of low self-efficacy in the online teaching-learning environment are not a complex interaction among students or between the students and the educator. The students that verbalize low self-efficacy do not discuss this low competence in great detail nor do they reiterate messages insisting on their lack of ability. The expression of low self-efficacy that we have found in these students is brief and does not go deeper into metacognitive aspects that would perhaps lead them to consider that their perception of low-efficacy is incorrect. Emotional aspects prevail over possible discussions in which the contents are worked on during the learning process or reflections on the fact that the types of activity were different but the content of the questions were very similar. Only 2 of the participants showing low self-efficacy verbalized metacognitive aspects that contribute to alleviating the emotional aspects related to low-efficacy. It is precisely those two participants who discussed their low self-efficacy while relating it to the difficulty of the task and the change in the type of activity, from practice into theory.

Teachers should keep this result in mind when monitoring courses; it can be interpreted as a request for help. The course teacher in our study sent a message to help. A reassuring message from the teacher, showing proof that the answers were correct in spite of the effort and the lack of competence verbalized by the students, causes a return to self-efficacy. Online teachers should therefore pay attention to these brief messages from students that show low self-efficacy and attempt to reassure and motivate them in their learning process. To our understanding, if these messages are not answered swiftly – in no more than two

days – the probability of student drop-out is high. In the following table, we show the message that led the eight students to return to self-efficacy.

Teacher Greetings,

Greetings,

The question that asks about the three categories of consumer ecological footprint should not overly concern you. Keep in mind that this question was a quiz question, not an exam question. This means that the teacher is not asking you to give the categories a theoretical content, but rather that you simply explain how you worked with the ecological footprint in this activity.

The two questions in the quiz have been formatted so that they can be answered in one paragraph, therefore, it is enough to explain what an ecological footprint means and how you found yours. This question corresponds to question 1 from the activity, so it is enough if you have answered the activity model.

Remember that the only two possible scores in this quiz are valid or invalid. Since I have been teaching here, there has only been one student who has received an invalid score.

Best regards.

Table 2: Written communication from the teacher to the students.

On the other hand, methodological attention must be paid to assumptions about teaching and learning processes. Methodology based on analyzing student and teacher discourse has been shown to be a natural way that respects the learning process. We suggest that processes be observed without evaluating student and the teacher behaviors, cognitions, and beliefs with a questionnaire or test (the MSLQ for example). To the contrary, we consider it to be essential to respect the virtual classroom activity just as it is produced. There are two reasons that lead us towards this statement. The first is the result according to which self-efficacy fragments appear more often when the perception of self-efficacy is negative and, therefore, students consider that their performance will be poor. The spontaneous verbalization of low self-efficacy has value in itself. This is why encouraging reflection on efficacy can have negative effects on the learning process. And secondly, recent research links the characteristics of online environments to the type of interaction that is produced (Hannafin & Lan, 1997; Shin, 2002; Shin, 2003). If this is correct, it is important to collect the data in the environment in which it occurs, being sure to exclude resources that are specific to the research.

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